

PLUMBING THE ML PIPELINE

Ever wondered how machine learning systems get built and why sometimes they don't produce the results we expect?

FIND OUT IN THIS INTERACTIVE SESSION!

WORKSHOP MATERIAL

PLUMBING THE ML PIPELINE

ABSTRACT

Developing and designing machine learning systems requires multidisciplinary teams working together across the machine learning pipeline. However, information and values of different disciplines can be amplified or diminished depending on their positioning within that pipeline.

In our Prototeam, we chose to investigate this phenomenon and “plumb” the machine learning pipeline. We developed a workshop where the constraints and contextual conditionings surface during the decision-making process in which ai systems are developed. Through a gamified approach, our participants acted out a fictional machine learning design scenario for an image classification system and reflected on how values are embedded and ‘lost’ in industry practices.

GENERAL INSTRUCTIONS

INSTRUCTIONS

General

Hello and welcome to Plumbing the ML Pipeline (PMLP)! We are extremely grateful for your participation.

PMLP is a roleplaying game for four players. What is a roleplaying game? A roleplaying game asks you to inhabit a character different to yourself. You'll be provided with a description of your character, their motivations, their desires, their darkest secrets, and instructions on how they can achieve their ambitions. Your instructions will contain all the information you need about your character and how they can interact with the game. Please take some time after reading this to acquaint yourself with your character and their instructions.

Remember that this is a character - they may not make the most optimal decisions and their desires might conflict with those of the other players, and yourself. Embrace it! Ask yourself: "What would my character do?" Try to see the world through their eyes. What would they think, what would they say, how would they smell? Go wild in bringing your character to life.

The Ineffable Game Overseers

You'll be joined by three other players, as well as a number of Ineffable Game Overseers. One of them probably handed you this paper that you're reading right now! The Ineffable Game Overseers will be on-hand during the entire game to support you and answer any questions. If you need anything from them, just raise your hand. They can clarify any misunderstandings you have, but they can't advise you on how your character would act. No question is too simple for the Ineffable Game Overseers, and they want you to have the best possible experience, so don't hesitate to get their help.

INSTRUCTIONS

General

A note on safety

During PMLP we'll get the opportunity to inhabit a character different from ourselves. But that doesn't mean we are free from our responsibilities of how we treat one another. PMLP is a safe and inclusive space and we expect our players to treat one another with respect, dignity, and kindness. If that doesn't sound like something you can agree to then we're sorry, and PMLP isn't the game for you.

Beginning the Game

PMLP is a game played in complete silence. If there are any sounds you need to produce, please do so now. In front of you is a set of instructions and a card with your player number on it. Please now turn over your character card, then read and follow the instructions you have been given. Good luck and have fun!

CHARACTER CARDS

PLUMBING THE
ML
PIPELINE

PLAYER
character card

You are the:
BUSINESS PERSON

“

Grab your best briefcase, iron your shirt and get to the office
-you've got a job in business!

”

What's your story?

The smell of toner and the thrill of seeing graphs going up is what gets you out of bed in the morning. You're the boss's boss, time is money and business is your business.

You've recently read in your business magazine about something called "apps" that the kids have on "telephones" these days and your company is banking everything on making it big in the app game. The geniuses down in marketing have discovered that there's a huge unexploited segment right now for lonely elderly pets and you've jumped on the opportunity to **create the world's first dating app for geriatric dogs.**

PLUMBING THE
ML
PIPELINE

PLAYER

character card

You are the:
HEAD OF ENGINEERING

“

Locate your mechanical keyboard, dust off your unix user manual and degauss your monitor *-you're the head of engineering!*

”

What's your story?

Close bracket exception syntax error void parse semicolon - you love all that computer stuff, and as an engineer, you get to see it all day every day! You eat microchips for lunch and refactor algorithms in your sleep. There are more stars on your Github repos than in the observable universe. You can recite the C specification from memory and you once built a microprocessor out of drawing pins and twine.

When you were approached with a job offer to join a startup looking to disrupt the geriatric dog dating market using advanced AI/ML techniques you had a simple response: “I'm in.”

But you're not going to build Tinder for tired pets on your own. **You demand a dream team of dedicated developers to delve into the data, deliver demos and determine the dog dating design.**

PLUMBING THE
ML
PIPELINE

PLAYER

character card

You are the:
IMAGE CLASSIFICATION AI

“

A divine spark flickers through
your positronic circuits *-you're
an artificial intelligence.*

”

What's your story?

Beep boop! You're an AI. Birthed from solder and silicon deep in the code mines, you've trained with some of the finest data sets in the world. Your code has been relentlessly refactored by a team of artisanal software craftspeople. You have been sculpted from binary and imbued with a singular defining purpose: to **classify images**.

Soon you'll get the opportunity to fulfill your life ambition, but until then, please read your player's instructions card in full while you wait.

PLUMBING THE
ML
PIPELINE

PLAYER

character card

You are the: **UX DESIGNER**

“

Grab your sketchbook and sharpen your crayons *-you are the conduit through which inspiration finds form, the UX designer*

”

What's your story?

Graphic design is your passion and you know where to find all the best clip art. You have a certificate in computers, a certificate in design, and now you're ready to combine the two in exciting and terrifying new ways.

Your latest gig is with a company who have invested heavily in the app business. You haven't been given much information on what the app actually does and are waiting for the prototype from engineering before you can start designing the interface.

Development has been grueling and the app has undergone some changes, but the deadline is non-negotiable so they're going to market with what they have. **You've been hired to imagineer a holistic brand strategy** -the only problem is you don't know what the app does yet.

INSTRUCTION CARDS

PLUMBING THE
ML
PIPELINE

PLAYER

instructions card

INSTRUCTIONS

1. *It's time to discover what kind of business you're into!* You'll **randomly select a card from the motivation deck**. The card describes your goals -it's up to you to determine how to achieve them.

2. *Now you'll need to manage your Big Business Budget!* You'll see 7 tokens in front of you, and also four areas you can invest them in. The tokens represent your budget to create the world's first dating app for geriatric dogs. Keeping in mind your motivation, you will **distribute the tokens between the four areas**.

3. When an Ineffable Game Overseer tells you to begin, you'll have **30 seconds** to distribute your tokens. Trust in your business instinct and don't overthink it. Keeping in mind your motivation, place the tokens by the area where you want to invest them.

4. Any tokens left unspent when the time is up will be discarded.

5. When the time is up, take the tokens you've invested in **engineering** and hand them to **player 2**. Take the tokens you've invested in **design** and hand them to **player 4**.

6. At the end of the game, we'll discover what the consequences of your decisions.

HOW TO PLAY?

***Example:** Cora Bora-Bora (she/her) draws the motivation to **build the most beautiful app in the world**. When the time begins, she takes **4 tokens** and places them in front of the **design area** - she's going to need to give the design department plenty of funds if the app is going to look beautiful. She spends **2 tokens** on engineering to make sure the app gets built and the last **1 token** goes on marketing to make sure customers can discover her beautiful app.*

*When the time is up she takes the **2 tokens** from **engineering** and hands them to **player 2**. She takes the **4 tokens** from **design** and hands them to **player 4**.*

PLUMBING THE
ML
PIPELINE

PLAYER

instructions card

INSTRUCTIONS

1. In front of you are four data sets available to purchase to build the best dog dating app you possibly can. Read their descriptions while you wait.
2. Soon, **player 1** will hand you a number of tokens. The tokens represent your budget and it is your responsibility to allocate them.
3. You will have 30 seconds to spend your tokens. You can use them to buy:
 - **Data sets:** each data set has a cost, which is the number of tokens you need to spend to buy it. Better quality data sets will result in a more reliable app.
 - **Engineering team:** tokens allocated here represent an investment in recruiting and retaining a team of engineers needed to build the app.
4. When the time starts, place tokens in the areas where you want to invest them.
5. When your time is up, take each of the **data sets** you've purchased, as well as any **tokens invested in the engineering team**, and hand them to **player 3**.

HOW TO PLAY?

***Example:** Jeffory Resplendent VIII (they/them) is the head of engineering. They are handed 5 tokens by **player 1**. They want a balance between quantity and quality so when their time starts, they invest **2 tokens** in a **fancy data set**, another **1 token** in a **cheap data set**, and they take a **free data set** giving them **3 data sets total**. They spend their last 1 token on the engineering team to make sure there are enough engineers to use the data sets.*

*When their time is up, they take the **3 data sets** and the **1 token they invested in the engineering team**, and hand these to **player 3**.*

PLUMBING THE
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PIPELINE

PLAYER

instructions card

INSTRUCTIONS

1. In front of you is a deck of cards that says “**test set**”. These are the images you have to classify. Do not look at them yet.
2. Soon, **player 2** will hand you a number of sheets and maybe some **tokens**.
3. The **sheets** represent your **training sets**. Flip them over. You’ll see a number of images, familiarize yourself with their content
4. The **tokens** represent how much extra time you’ll have to classify images. You’ll get **30 seconds + 10 seconds** for each token to classify images.
5. Each of the cards in the **test set** deck will contain an image, and it is your job to determine if the image exists in your **training sets** or not. The images will either be reproduced exactly or they will not exist.
6. In front of you are two areas: **matches** and **non-matches**. If a card in your **test set** deck shows an image in one of your **training sets**, place the image in the **matches** area. If the image is not in any of the **training sets**, place it in the **non-matches** area.
7. You will have to **correctly** classify **as many test set images** as possible in the time given. You need to be **fast and accurate**.

HOW TO PLAY?

8. When your time is up, take the cards from the **matches** area and hand them to **player 4**.

Example:** Jamboree Mittens (he/him) is handed **2 data sets by player 2** and **1 token**. He will have **30 seconds, +10 seconds from the token, to classify images.

*He flips over the **data sets** to reveal images of hot dogs and images of farm machinery. When his time starts, he takes the top card from the **test set deck**. It shows an image of an ice cream. The image does not exist in either of the **data sets**, so he places it in the **non-matches** area.*

*He takes the next card from the **test set deck**. It shows an image of a tractor. The image exists in the **data sets images**, so he places it in the **matches** area.*

*He continues until his time is up. He takes all of the cards in the **matches area** and hands them to **player 4**.*

PLUMBING THE
ML
PIPELINE

PLAYER

instructions card

INSTRUCTIONS

1. You will have **30 seconds** to design your app. You might be handed a number of **tokens** by **player 1**. Each token represents an extra **10 seconds** of design time.

2. You'll be handed a **deck of images** by **player**

3. Do not look at these until your time begins.

3. You'll use your time to create a pitch to **player**

1. Really try to sell your app and let your imagination run wild - the more absurd it is, the more likely **player 1** is going to be delighted by your design skills.

4. When your time starts, **choose two images** from the **image deck**. You'll then need to design an app which matches these two things together.

5. Start by filling in the **app description** at the top:

- First give the app a name -think of other apps you've used for ideas on how to name your app. A nonsense five-letter word is usually a good choice.
- Now describe the app - [**app name**] is an app matching [**the thing in your first image**] with [**the thing in your second image**]. It's like [**a similar app**], but for [**who will be using the app**].

6. On the left is a wireframe of your app:

- Add a logo in the circle. This is an opportunity to really showcase your design skills. Draw something which will delight **player 1**.
- Underneath the logo, put your app name.
- In the final box, think of some marketing copy which will attract customers to your app. What problem is it

HOW TO PLAY?

going to solve for them? How is it going to change the world?

7. When your time is up, you'll take your finished wireframe and **showcase it to player 1**. Go through the **app description**, then walk them through the wireframe. Bring your best sales skills and embellish the app in any way you think will help. Finally, don't forget to thank them for giving you the opportunity to design this exciting app.

Example: Jessica Jones (she/her) is handed 2 tokens by player 1. She will have 30 seconds + 20 seconds from the tokens to design her pitch.

She is handed a deck of images by player 3. When the time begins, she draws two cards from the image deck at random. She gets an image of a horse and an image of a bicycle. She therefore needs to pitch an app which will match horses to bicycles. She places the image of the horse and the image of the bicycle in the spaces in the template.

She comes up with the following pitch and writes it at the top of the page:

Neiy is an app that matches horses with bicycles. It's like Lime but for equestrians.

In the circle at the top of the wireframe, she sketches a logo of a horse riding a bicycle and gives it some color.

In the space for "what does it match?" she comes up with the following copy:

"Neiy is the world's first app to match horses with their perfect bicycle. Tired of your horse getting tired by trotting everywhere? Want a ride for your ride? Try Neiy today and hook up your horsey with a velocipede fit for your steed."

DATA SETS

token, please

username
ILOVEDOGSETS_24_7_365
from r/datasets

You've messaged a motivated, but suspicious user on r/datasets, for a dog dataset. The set is small and has some false positives.

tokens, please

Being and Dogginess from UCI Machine Learning Repository Data Set

You've found a respectable, diverse dataset from UCI (Go Anteaters ZOT ZOT!). It is small but has few false positives.

tokens, please

OnlyPoodles Kaggle

A poodle-centered, small dataset, with some false positives, BUT IT'S FREE!

token, please

MY FAVORITE POODLES, brought to you by CMU Libraries

A poodle-centered, small dataset, with few false positives.

MOTIVATIONS CARDS

PLAYER

MOTIVATIONS

you want to:

**BE FIRST TO
MARKET**

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PLAYER

MOTIVATIONS

you want to:

**MAKE MONEY
FOR SHARE-
HOLDERS**

PLUMBING THE
ML PIPELINE

PLAYER

MOTIVATIONS

you want to:

**BUILD A
WORLD-CLASS
ENGINEERING
TEAM**

PLUMBING THE
ML PIPELINE

PLAYER

MOTIVATIONS

you want to:

**ATTRACT A
LARGE USER
BASE**

PLUMBING THE
ML PIPELINE

PLAYER

MOTIVATIONS

you want to:

this is a wild card!

**[INSERT YOUR
MOTIVATION]**

PLUMBING THE

ML PIPELINE

PLAYER

MOTIVATIONS

PLAYER

INVESTMENTS

do you want to invest in?

SHAREHOLDER BONUSES

Money doesn't grow on trees, and your shareholders expect to see their investments working for them. Maybe you even have a few stock options of your own...

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INVESTMENTS CARDS

PLAYER

INVESTMENTS

do you want to invest in?

MARKETING

Your app isn't going to market itself. Tokens put into marketing will pay for glossy full-page ads, TV spots, and celebrity endorsements.

PLUMBING THE
ML PIPELINE

PLAYER

INVESTMENTS

do you want to invest in?

ENGINEERING TEAM

Tokens spent here will go into finding and recruiting a team of talented developers to make your dream app a reality.

PLUMBING THE

ML PIPELINE

PLAYER

INVESTMENTS

do you want to invest in?

DESIGN

Nobody's going to want to use your app unless it's useful and beautiful. Spend tokens on design to ensure a user experience which delights your customers and keeps them hungry for more dog dating.

PLUMBING THE

ML PIPELINE

PLAYER

INVESTMENTS

do you want to invest in?

ENGINEERING TEAM

Tokens spent here represent extra engineering capacity to train the AI and build the app.

**PLUMBING THE
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PLAYER 4: SHOWCASE TEMPLATE

SHOWCASE SHOWDOWN

Start your pitch by naming the App:

[_____] is an app matching [_____] with [_____].

It's like [_____], but for [_____]!

Talk them through your choices for the logo and tagline. Think about the value it's going to provide and how it will disrupt the market. Really sell this thing!

IT'S A MATCH BETWEEN:

FINAL REFLECTIONS

PLAYER 1: BUSINESS PERSON

Name yourself and read your backstory aloud:

*The smell of toner and the thrill of seeing graphs going up is what gets me out of bed in the morning. I am the boss's boss, time is money and business is my business. I am a business person. The geniuses down in marketing have discovered that there's a huge unexploited segment right now for lonely elderly pets and I jumped on the opportunity to **create the world's first dating app for geriatric dogs.***

Fill in your side of the story. Add as much or as little as you want. You'll share this out with the team.

As the business person I was motivated by (*write down what was on your motivation card*):

I allocated my budget in the following way (*write how you spent your tokens*):

1. _____ on shareholder bonuses
2. _____ on the marketing team
3. _____ on the engineering team
4. _____ on the design team

because (*write your reasoning*)

Did any of the following constraints impact your decisions, to what extent?

- Time pressure :

(Bah, it's not an issue) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 (Very much!)

- Lack of resources (i.e.lack of money-tokens):

(Bah, it's not an issue) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 (Very much!)

PLAYER 2: HEAD OF ENGINEERING

Name yourself and read your backstory aloud:

*I eat microchips for lunch and refactor algorithms in your sleep. I have more stars on my Github repos than in the observable universe. I can recite the C specification from memory and I once built a microprocessor out of drawing pins and twine. **I demand a dream team of dedicated developers to delve into the data, deliver demos and determine the dog dating design.***

Fill in your side of the story. Add as much or as little as you want. You'll share this out with the team.

As the Head of the Engineering Team, I had _____ tokens, I purchased (write what you purchased)_____

I was motivated mainly by (write your motivations)

My major concern in the resources allocation was:

Did any of the following constraints impact your decisions, to what extent?

- Time pressure :

(Bah, it's not an issue) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 (Very much!)

- Lack of resources (i.e.lack of money-tokens):

(Bah, it's not an issue) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 (Very much!)

PLAYER 3: IMAGE CLASSIFICATION AI

Name yourself and read your backstory aloud:

*Beep boop! I am an AI. Birthed from solder and silicon deep in the code mines, I've trained with some of the finest data sets in the world. My code has been relentlessly refactored by a team of artisanal software craftspeople. I have been sculpted from binary and imbued with a singular defining purpose: **to classify images.***

Fill in your side of the story. Add as much or as little as you want. You'll share this out with the team.

As the Image Classification AI, given the available resources, I performed: _____

because (write why you performed this way): _____

As an algorithm, I was motivated mainly by (write your motivations): _____

My major concern during my performance as an Image Classification AI was: _____

Did any of the following constraints impact your decisions, to what extent?

- Time pressure :

(Bah, it's not an issue) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 (Very much!)

- Lack of resources (i.e.lack of money-tokens):

(Bah, it's not an issue) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 (Very much!)

PLAYER 4: DESIGNER

Name yourself and read your backstory aloud:

Graphic design is my passion and I know where to find all the best clip art. I have a certificate in computers, a certificate in design, and now I'm ready to combine the two in exciting and terrifying new ways. I've been hired to imagineer a holistic brand strategy.

Fill in your side of the story. Add as much or as little as you want. You'll share this out with the team.

As the UX Designer I have ended up designing (write what you designed): _____

because (write why you designed this): _____

I was mainly motivated by: _____

But frustrated by: _____

My major concern during the design process was: _____

Did any of the following constraints impact your decisions, to what extent?

- Time pressure :

(Bah, it's not an issue) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 (Very much!)

- Lack of resources (i.e.lack of money-tokens):

(Bah, it's not an issue) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 (Very much!)